

Original Research

Using formative evaluation to adapt a co-creation process within and between workplace contexts: A Health CASCADE study

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Co-creation offers a promising approach to developing tailored health promotion interventions, but it requires adaptable processes responsive to contextual needs. Formative evaluation supports this adaptability through continuous reflection and informed adaptations. This study examines adaptations through formative evaluation in co-creation processes within and between different workplace contexts to advance the evaluation, transferability, and public health impact of co-creation.

Study design: A qualitative study examining adaptations to co-creation processes through thematic analysis.

Methods: A co-creation process to develop a context-specific solution to reduce workplace sedentary behaviour was implemented in three small-to-medium-sized enterprises (6–8 sessions per company). Data from a pilot session, project meetings, co-creator feedback, and facilitator reflections were systematically linked to the resulting adaptations they informed. Reasons for adaptations were derived through thematic analysis.

Results: Adaptations occurred at two stages: planned adaptations, made before implementing the co-creation process, based on pilot data and project meeting logs, and responsive adaptations, made during implementation, informed by co-creator evaluations and facilitator reflections. Three main reasons for adaptations emerged: tailoring to context, enhancing process effectiveness, and fostering engagement.

Conclusion: Formative evaluation is crucial in evaluating co-creation processes. It ensures that these processes remain relevant, effective, and engaging, with skilled facilitators and end-user input being key. Replicating co-creation processes in new contexts requires the documentation of previous adaptations to identify core elements while allowing flexibility. These insights support the design of adaptable, evidence-based co-creation processes and help advance their evaluation and implementation in diverse contexts to develop effective and tailored solutions.

1. Introduction

Participatory Action Research approaches, such as co-creation, engage stakeholders in developing and implementing initiatives.¹ These are seen as promising methodologies for enhancing public health interventions, including in workplace health promotion.^{2–4} Co-creation involves continuous active collaboration and shared decision-making among various stakeholders towards creative problem-solving covering all initiative phases, from problem identification to

evaluation.^{5,6}

A key aspect of co-creation is recognising that the initial protocol will likely evolve due to contextual challenges, co-creators' needs and decisions, and prior evidence, requiring flexibility in both planning and conducting co-creation.^{7–10} Formative evaluation can inform this adaptability through continuous evaluation, systematically collecting data throughout planning, conducting, and post-process stages, allowing timely adaptation of the co-creation process due to, for instance, misalignment of planned process elements with the specific

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context.^{9,11,12} These adaptations, whether planned (proactive) or responsive (sudden), ensure that the co-creation process remains relevant and effective.^{10,11,13,14} As part of formative evaluation, co-creators' reflections should be continuously collected, ensuring their voices guide the adaptations.^{9,11,15} This enhances cultural sensitivity and contextual relevance of the process, leading to a more efficient development of tailored, context-specific solutions.¹⁰

Co-creation requires evaluating both its outcomes and how the process unfolds, as the process itself strongly influences the success of the solution and the experience of co-creators.^{16–18} The growing focus on process evaluation in co-creation is reflected in the recently published PROSECO framework, which outlines key components for evaluating co-creation processes and methods.¹⁶ Formative evaluation plays a central role in process evaluation, supporting ongoing assessment and reflection throughout the co-creation process.^{11,18} Pearce and Magee¹⁸ similarly emphasise the necessity of continuous evaluation involving everyone, and note that clearer guidance on how to implement such practices is needed. Limited documentation of formative evaluation and past adaptation decisions hinders understanding of its relevance and impact on co-creation efforts.^{3,9,10} Studying how formative evaluation is applied in co-creation and how adaptations occur in response directly contributes to advancing knowledge on evaluating co-creation processes.^{9,18} Furthermore, it provides much-needed insight into the effective transfer of co-creation processes to new contexts, such as different settings or populations. When no suitable solution exists and resources are limited to develop a co-creation process from scratch, adapting an existing co-creation process to develop a new solution is necessary.¹⁰ A key challenge here lies in balancing the effectiveness of the original process with the flexibility needed for adapting the process.^{3,10,19} Yet, without clear records of the changes made and their rationale, learning from past experiences becomes difficult, creating uncertainty in transferring co-creation processes and limiting their scalability to diverse public health contexts.^{3,9,10,20}

This study focuses on the co-creation of actions to reduce sedentary behaviour (SB) at work. High levels of SB are linked to health risks such as type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular disease and increased mortality.^{21,22} Office workers are particularly affected, spending 60–79 % of their workday sitting.^{22,23} SB is a complex issue, deeply embedded in daily habits and influenced by social, political, and economic factors, like the

expectation that work is done seated at a desk.^{22,24–26} In the workplace context, co-creation is thought to enhance the design of feasible, acceptable, and effective solutions tailored to employees' needs and unique work environments, while also fostering employees' motivation and ownership of the solution.^{2,4,13,27} We examine the adaptations made within and between the co-creation processes, including a formal analysis to identify general reasons for adaptations, and how this contributes to enhancing the evaluation and transferability of a co-creation process.

2. Methods

This study used a qualitative design to examine adaptations within and between co-creation processes at three different Scottish companies aimed at developing actions to reduce SB at work.

2.1. Co-creation process: design, implementation, and participant recruitment

A co-creation process was conducted consecutively at three small-to-medium-sized enterprises (SME; <250 employees; referred to as Companies A, B and C) in Glasgow, involving between six and eight co-creation sessions each (Table 1). The planning of the initial co-creation process is detailed in a separate publication.²⁸ Weekly 1.5-h sessions, held on-site, were run by two facilitators ([Mi.V.], [L.Mc.C.]) with additional support from a third facilitator in Company A. The three co-creation processes followed a similar stepwise approach mirroring the Three Co's framework.¹⁸ It began with *Co-Defining*, which involved establishing group cohesion, building knowledge about SB, and mapping the company's situation. This was followed by *Co-Designing*, which entailed brainstorming and planning actions. *Co-Refining* included implementing a short-term action, reflecting and finalising the actions. The actions are called the 'solution' and were implemented by the companies' employees after the co-creation process. During planning, implementation, and afterwards, the co-creation processes were adapted based on evaluation data (described below), which informed both the current and subsequent co-creation processes (Fig. 1).

The SMEs were recruited through local health networks, social media, cold emailing, and a dedicated website. Each company formed a planning group (employees providing input, feedback, and support on

Table 1
Overview of participants, average attendance at co-creation sessions and project timescale.

	Company A	Company B	Company C
Company	Construction Management	Charity	Charity
Company size	150 employees	100 employees	30 employees
Company location	Glasgow	Glasgow	Glasgow
Planning group composition	3 employees: The contact person and two other employees, all of whom were Health and Safety Professionals. None participated in the action group.	6 employees: The contact person and five employees, including HR and Finance staff, and a range of other employees. All participated in the action group.	1 employee: The contact person, an employee in a managerial position. Participated in the action group.
Action group composition	10 employees as co-creators (7 male/3 female). Age ranged from 29 to 58 years (M = 41.3, SD = 10.6). The length of time in employment at the company ranged from less than a year to over 10 years. Six reported that they supervised/managed other staff. All held higher education qualifications.	9 employees as co-creators (7 female, 2 male). Age ranged from 19 to 55 years (M = 41, SD = 12). The length of time in employment at the company ranged from less than a year to 19 years, with most (n = 7) being employed at the company for four years or less. Seven reported that they supervised/managed other staff. Seven held higher education qualifications, and 2 had secondary education qualifications.	12 employees as co-creators (11 female, 1 male). Age ranged from 25 to 60 years (M = 38.33, SD = 12.28). The length of time in employment at the company ranged from one year to 23 years (M = 4.83, SD = 6.41). Three reported that they supervised/managed other staff. Ten held higher education qualifications, and 2 had secondary education qualifications.
Co-creation process	Eight sessions over a nine-week period.	Six sessions over a seven-week period.	Six sessions over a seven-week period.
Average attendance across all sessions	66 %	89 %	71 %
Timescale	Recruited: Aug 2022 Sessions: Oct–Dec 2022 Final Assessment: Oct 2023	Recruited: Aug 2022 Sessions: Jan–Mar 2023 Final Assessment: Dec 2023	Recruited: March 2023 Sessions: Apr–May 2023 Final Assessment: Jan 2024

Fig. 1. Illustration of adaptation of a co-creation process within and between projects through formative evaluation.

co-creator recruitment and session structure before conducting the co-creation process) and an action group of co-creators (those involved in the co-creation process,¹⁸ in this case employees, who collaborate continuously, produce knowledge and make shared decisions to create a solution). The planning groups included a company contact and additional staff such as Health and Safety professionals, HR, or Finance staff. The action group consisted of the company’s employees who volunteered to participate, with recruitment leveraged through internal communications via the company contact. In each company, the same group of between 9 and 12 employees participated throughout the co-creation process (Table 1). Not all co-creators attended every session due to work demands, annual leave, sickness, or personal reasons.

2.2. Measurements

The assessment of the co-creation processes included the pilot session log, planning groups’ logs, co-creators’ evaluation forms, and facilitators’ reflection logs (Table 2). These evaluation sources are referred to as ‘inputs’ moving forward.

Before the first co-creation process began, we piloted an initial session with colleagues. Before each co-creation process, a meeting was held with each company’s planning group. Meeting logs were documented by the facilitators shortly after the pilot session and each planning meeting, recording discussions, decisions, and action points. During the co-creation process, co-creators completed a brief evaluation

Table 2 Assessment schedule for the co-creation processes.

Evaluation sources (Inputs)	Participant group	Assessment timing
A pilot of Session 1	Researcher colleagues	Before any sessions
Planning meeting	Company planning group	Before Session 1 at each company
Co-creator evaluation forms ^a	Company action group	At the end of every session at each company
Lead and second facilitator session debrief	Facilitators of the co-creation sessions	Immediately after every session at each company
Lead facilitator reflection log		
Preliminary feedback from co-creator interviews by the second facilitator ¹⁷	Company action group	Within 1 month of the end of sessions at each company

^a Due to time constraints, no co-creator evaluation forms were collected for sessions 5, 6, and 8 in Company A. However, the direction of future sessions was discussed with co-creators in all sessions. In Companies B and C, facilitators improved time management, ensuring evaluation forms were collected for all sessions.

form at the end of each co-creation session (Supplementary Material 2), asking what they wanted to focus on next, the session’s perceived usefulness, and their sense of inclusion, supplemented by an Emotion Scale with colour-coded faces to simplify feedback. An open-ended section allowed for additional comments. After the co-creators had completed the forms, the facilitators led a brief group discussion to gather further insights and clarify their answers. After each co-creation session, the lead and second facilitator held an on-site debrief to discuss their reflections. Additionally, the lead facilitator completed structured post-session reflection logs, which captured their immediate observations on what worked, potential improvements, and their overall impressions (Supplementary Material 3). These logs included sections for planned changes, along with their rationales. Between co-creation processes in the different companies, informal discussions with the second facilitator allowed preliminary feedback from interviews with co-creators to be incorporated, although a formal analysis of these interviews was not yet completed.¹⁷

2.3. Data analysis

To identify general reasons for adaptations to co-creation processes, we adopted a structured approach to organise and analyse the data, compiling data from the meeting logs, co-creator feedback forms, and facilitator reflection logs into a table. Adaptations made during and between iterations were extracted by the lead facilitator from facilitator logs and checked against the final overview of the sessions conducted. We used colour coding to map the links between evaluation inputs and their resulting adaptations.

A collaborative and reflexive thematic analysis was conducted on the collated data using an inductive, data-driven approach to identify patterns of adaptation and group into themes for interpretation, following Braun and Clarke’s six-stage framework.^{29,30} Two researchers ([Mi.V.], [L.D.]) familiarised themselves with the data. Mi.V. facilitated the co-creation sessions for this study, while L.D. has facilitated co-creation within a school context but was not involved in this study’s sessions. They independently coded all the collated adaptation data and generated initial themes independently. Adaptations could be coded to multiple themes. Subsequently, they met to review, refine, define, and name the themes (Supplementary Material 4). They then independently applied the thematic framework to the collated adaptation data from all three companies using NVivo 13 (2020, R1). Coding discrepancies were discussed to achieve a nuanced understanding and consensus.

3. Results

3.1. Timing and decision-making of adaptations

Adaptation to the co-creation processes occurred at two stages. Planned adaptations were made before implementation in the workplace, based on data from the session pilot and planning groups. Responsive adaptations emerged during the co-creation process itself, informed by the co-creators' evaluations and facilitators' reflections. Facilitator Mi.V. sought to address all relevant evaluation inputs and proposed changes; however, not all resulted in adaptations. An adaptation was *not* made when (1) the proposed change was already in the planned content; (2) it was unfeasible due to time or resource constraints; or (3) it was not widely supported or repeated by other co-creators or by the facilitators. However, feasible suggestions from single co-creators were still considered. Adaptations were communicated to the action group when they stemmed from co-creator feedback. Adaptations were also made between processes when transferring the co-creation process to a new workplace context, drawing on the facilitators' reflections and insight from the interviews conducted by the second facilitator.¹⁷ Fig. 2 shows a visual summary of how the co-creation process was adapted within and between its consecutive implementations in different workplace contexts. Most adaptations involved changing, adding, or removing activities and methods, adjusting session content, and restructuring how sessions were organised.

3.2. Reasons for adaptations

The findings from the thematic analysis show that adaptations to co-creation processes served three interconnected goals: (1) adapting to fit the context, (2) enhancing the effectiveness of the co-creation process, and (3) fostering co-creator engagement (Fig. 3). Examples of adaptations for each goal are provided below. The full list of adaptations, including evaluation inputs, rationale for decisions, and associated themes, is available in [Supplementary Material 4](#). Quotes have been attributed to co-creators using pseudonyms.

3.2.1. Adaptations to context

3.2.1.1. *Adaptations specific to participating companies.* The process was tailored to meet the unique needs of each workplace. Establishing a

planning group within each company proved essential. They informed initial changes to the co-creation process's session timing and structure. Company A suggested adding a presentation to clarify the initiative for all employees before starting recruitment and alternating sessions between their two sites to share travel time across employees. Throughout the co-creation process, co-creator feedback further refined the process to meet their individual and company-specific needs. In Company B, a discussion was added on whether and how to incorporate wider workforce opinion into the actions being co-created, and in Company C, the brainstorming activity was adapted to encourage selecting actions specifically aimed at altering attitudes towards change within their organisation.

3.2.1.2. *Adaptations related to the workplace environment.* The co-creation process was adapted to enhance its alignment with the workplace environment in general. In Companies B and C, homework tasks were removed to avoid the additional workload outside sessions. Also, the method for exploring communication possibilities was adapted, shifting its focus from general communication possibilities—which companies are typically aware of—to specific workplace communication challenges (e.g., in-office vs. remote communication).

3.2.1.3. *Adaptations related to the topic.* Learning about the target issue during the co-creation process is essential for developing solutions. The information on the topic—its content and delivery method—was adapted to align with the differing needs and contexts of co-creators, thereby encouraging their collaboration and discussion. In Company A, a strong interest in learning about the risks of workplace sitting led to longer and more detailed knowledge-building activities on SB. Also, co-creators' interest in exploring "ways to be more active during breaks and while working" (Grace, Company B, Session1) led to including joint walking and stretching breaks in sessions in Companies B and C, providing practical activities for co-creators to integrate into their daily routines.

3.2.2. Adaptations for an effective co-creation process

3.2.2.1. *Adaptations to improve the process's efficiency.* The structure and schedule of the sessions were adapted to improve their effectiveness. At Company A, co-creators showed strong interest in developing

Fig. 2. Overview and evolution due to adaptations of the co-creation process implemented consecutively in three UK workplaces.

Fig. 3. Thematic results regarding the reasons for adaptations to the co-creation processes.

concrete actions to reduce SB, and facilitators were concerned about “possible disengagement if we keep talking and not taking action (Session4).” Consequently, to enable an earlier transition to action planning, the co-creation processes for Companies B and C were condensed from eight to six sessions; the content of Session 4 was redistributed to other sessions, Sessions 5 and 6 were merged, and the overall pace was increased, supported by the facilitators’ enhanced time management skills. Co-creator feedback in Companies B and C reaffirmed the need for these changes, as they, too, were keen to reach the action planning stage. A facilitator remarked in Company C, “There seems to be more understanding of the process. This is perhaps because developing the actions comes a lot sooner than in [Company A’s process], for example (Session1).”

3.2.2.2. Adaptations related to flexibility in activities and methods. Activities and methods were adapted, introduced, or removed based on their relevance and effectiveness in supporting the action group’s progress. The timing of some activities and methods was changed. The ‘Select the Internal Change Champion’ activity, which originally took place in Session 1 in Company A, was moved to the final sessions in Companies B and C to better support the action group’s continuation. New activities and methods were introduced as necessary. A group discussion in Session 5 at Company B addressed Carol’s suggestion to “look at other ideas to get more people involved (Session4)”, and Molly’s question on how to “continue to encourage each other in following our action plan (Session4).” Activities and methods that lacked added value were removed to streamline the process. The ‘benefits of policies and actions on SB in the workplace’ activity was removed, as co-creators already developed an understanding through knowledge-building activities. However, it is important to keep track of previously omitted activities and methods, as they may have been excluded for reasons other than redundancy and could be reintroduced if necessary. The ‘creating a mission statement’ activity, initially omitted in Company A due to time constraints, was later reinstated in Company B when Fiona expressed a desire to “understand more about the aims of the group ... (Session1).”

3.2.2.3. Adaptations related to facilitator adaptability and approach. A co-creation process requires responsive and flexible facilitation. In Company A, confusion over in-person versus hybrid attendance caused some co-creators to miss Session 1. Consequently, the facilitator repeated its introductory activities in Session 2 for new members, delaying or skipping other planned activities. Also in Company A, a session had unexpectedly low attendance ($n = 4$), prompting the facilitators to defer the action planning activities to the next session to ensure diverse contributions and reconfigure future sessions. Furthermore, the co-creation process benefits from facilitators honing their facilitation techniques, particularly in relation to the needs of the co-creators. Several co-creators in Company A sought greater clarity on the purpose of activities and sessions. Jane expressed a desire for “a better understanding of the aim of the workgroup on that task,” while Lewis questioned, “the benefit of the session in terms of the overall outcome (Session2).” In response, facilitators began highlighting session goals at the beginning and end of sessions and connecting activities to the overarching aim of the co-creation process. In Company B, the facilitator trained to better guide the group’s discussion, keeping them more focused while reducing the need for adaptations due to time constraints.

3.2.3. Adaptations to improve co-creator engagement

The co-creation process was adapted to encourage ownership, enhance participation, and address retention challenges. To encourage ownership, session pilot feedback led to adding an activity in Session 1, where co-creators mapped the contributions and expertise they brought to the group, fostering a sense of responsibility for their roles. To enhance participation, facilitators prioritised knowledge-building activities earlier in the process to support the co-creators’ motivation to address SB. To address attendance challenges, a discussion was introduced in Session 6 at Company C to develop strategies to boost attendance. This addressed facilitator concerns about the lack of managerial attendance hindering feedback on decisions, as well as co-creator Martina’s question raised during Session 5: “Is the group getting smaller?” How can we maintain momentum?”

4. Discussion

This study examined how a co-creation process for developing actions to reduce SB at work was adapted within and between various workplace contexts. The findings underscore the important role of formative evaluation, particularly by gathering end-user input, for evaluating co-creation processes. The continuous evaluation informed adaptations before (proactive) and during (sudden) the co-creation process, involving restructuring sessions, modifying activities and methods, and adjusting content, often within a short timescale (e.g., between weekly sessions). Ultimately, continuous refinement through formative evaluation led to an increasingly well-structured and efficient co-creation process, which can serve as a guide for future projects. Skilled and flexible facilitation was essential, requiring adapting to unexpected circumstances (e.g., low attendance) and diverse group dynamics (e.g., a discursive group). These adaptations aimed to keep the process contextually relevant, effective, and engaging for co-creators. This underscores the need to evaluate context, co-creators' experiences, and participation to yield critical insights for adaptation, in line with the recently published PROSECO process evaluation framework, which also emphasises assessment of these key dimensions of co-creation, along with evaluation of impact and delivery.¹⁶

Understanding of these adaptations enhances our insight into the transferability of co-creation processes in new contexts. While developing a new process has its merits, leveraging existing ones can save time, resources, and prevent repeated mistakes. It enhances facilitator preparedness and flexibility, thereby improving the co-creation experience and outcomes.^{17,31} However, rigidly following the original process can stifle creativity and limit necessary adaptations to suit a new context.³ To maintain what made the original process effective while allowing flexibility in its application in a new context, documentation of past iterations—including adaptations and their rationales—is crucial. It can help identify a process's core elements, i.e., the mechanisms by which the process achieves its outcome, that must be preserved.¹⁰ In this study, detailed records and insight from facilitators and co-creators, supported by literature, helped reflect on which elements, such as multiple sessions and jointly set ground rules,^{2,32} were essential. Consulting those involved in earlier iterations, gathering insights from past participants, or forming advisory boards is recommended to gather this past knowledge.¹⁰ Furthermore, similar to functional fidelity, the core elements in this study were flexible in their form, meaning the activities and methods used to achieve their purpose can be adapted to new contexts as long as their overall purpose remains unchanged.^{19,33} For example, the method for knowledge-building on SB may vary by company culture, using creative approaches in some environments and analytical ones in others. By using a flexible approach that preserves core elements while tailoring its activities and methods to local needs, public health researchers and practitioners can implement evidence-based and context-sensitive processes, paving the way for the more efficient development of tailored, effective and sustainable public health solutions through co-creation.

A key strength of this study is its inclusion of data from three co-creation processes, providing broader insights than typical single-case evaluations in co-creation process research. Some limitations should be acknowledged. The facilitators of the co-creation sessions also conducted evaluations with the co-creators, potentially influencing the co-creators' responses (e.g. reluctance to criticise the process). Additionally, interview data on co-creators' experiences by the second facilitator were used to adapt the process before a full data analysis was completed. Although this enabled early integration of insights, it may have limited the depth of interpretation at that stage. The study was conducted in three Glaswegian SMEs, which provided similar contexts despite their structural differences and diversity in employee backgrounds. Moreover, the workplace setting may have influenced the identified rationale for adaptations, making some context-specific rather than universal, and thus limiting generalisability. Future research should explore adapting

co-creation processes in more diverse contexts. This study's insights can contribute to practical guidelines for evaluating co-creation processes.

In conclusion, based on this study's approach, we present recommendations for managing adaptation through formative evaluation in co-creation:

- When planning a co-creation project, build in clear methods and regular points for collecting formative feedback from all co-creators and facilitators
- Design the co-creation process to be flexible, using methods and activities that can easily be adjusted
- When gathering feedback, specifically request insights related to enhancing context fit, process effectiveness, and co-creator engagement to guide adaptations.
- Record and document the adaptations that were made: what was changed, why, who decided, and when
- Use adaptation documentation as a learning tool. When transferring a process to a new context, review past adaptations to anticipate potential challenges, identify elements that were consistently effective (core elements), and plan for areas likely to require flexibility and responsive adaptation. This helps balance preserving the process's effectiveness with adapting to the new context
- Recognise the crucial role of skilled, flexible facilitators

Author statements

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for the case study was granted by the Glasgow Caledonian University Research Ethics Committee (approval number: HLS/PSWAHS/21/229), and all employees involved in the action group provided informed consent prior to commencing the co-creation process.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Patients and/or public involvement

Patients and/or the public were not involved in this study.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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